

Original Research Article

Factors Affecting Academic Performance of Students at Community Secondary School in Nepal

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Abstract

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This study examined the perception of the students on the academic performance at community secondary school in Tokha Municipality, Bagmati Province, Nepal. This study aimed at examining the influence of school, teacher, student and parent related factor on students' academic performance in secondary schools. A total of eighty (80) secondary schools students from five selected schools participated in this study. The study used purposive sampling. It employed quantitative data collection tools which included questionnaire survey. The data obtained through questionnaires were edited, categorized tallied, and tabulated. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Percentage was used to explain the characteristics of the respondents. The results indicated that the students' academic performance in the study area was determined by different factors. Among these factors, school related factors were school climate, availability of teaching materials, methods of delivery were the most prominent factors that affect students' academic performance. Teacher's motivation, relation with their students, punctuality by teachers, use of instructional materials, inadequate teacher preparedness, non-marking of student's exercises etc. were the major teacher related factors that directly affect students' academic performance. Student related major factors which affect the student's performance were student's self-motivation, less amount of time invested on educational activities, absence of regular school attendance, relation with teachers, relation with other schoolmates, lack of adequate effort etc. And major parent related factors which affect the students' performance were parents socio economic status, parents academic background, parental occupation level, attitude towards academic performance, poor parental child interaction. The policy makers, school authority, teachers and parents must aware to improve the students' academic performance at secondary schools.

Keywords: Academic performance, Parent, Secondary school, Student, Teacher

INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization and technological revolution, education is considered as a first step for every human activity (Farooq et al., 2011). Education helps individuals to function well in their environment. Education plays a vital role in the development of human capital and is linked with an individual's well-being and opportunities for better living (Battle and Lewis, 2002). In particular, secondary education is an important sector in individual and national development. It plays a vital role in creating a country's human resource base at a level higher than primary education (Achoka et al., 2007).

Students are the most essential component for any educational institute. Schools, colleges and universities have no worth without students (Irfan and Shabana, 2012). Student performance occupies a very important space in education in educational process. Student's academic performance is a key feature in academic institution. Academic performance which is measured by the examination results, is one of the major goals of the school. Academic performance is generally regarded as the display of knowledge attained or skills developed in the school subject (Busari, 2000). In any educational

institutions, success is measured by academic performance or how well a learner meets standards set by the every educational institution.

Parents care about their child's academic performance because they believe good academic results will provide more carrier choice and job security. Students' performance impact on their career choice, personal income and level of success, as well as the degree of participation in community life (Grainen,1995). Schools though invested in same reason are also often influenced by concerns about the school's reputation (Bhat and Khandai, 2016). It ensures the acquisition of knowledge and skills that enable individuals to increase their productivity and improve their quality of life. This increase in productivity also leads towards new sources of earning which enhances the economic growth of a country (Saxton, 2000).The socio-economic development of the country is directly related with academic performance of the students. The students' performance plays an important role in producing the best quality graduates who will become efficient manpower for the country (Ali et al., 2009).

Different factors are inside and outside school that affect students' academic performance. The un-encouraging academic performance is linked to factors such as; students' lack of interest and undesirable attitude to the subject (especially practical agriculture), inadequate or nonexistent of teaching instructional materials and inadequate funding (Otekunrin and Otekunrin, 2020). In previous studies (Dlamini, 1995; Otekunrin et al., 2019), identified some key variables related to academic performance of students and classified them as; (i) school-related variables (time spent studying, time spent in the library, interest in the subject, distance of home from school among others); (ii) home background-related variables (educational level of the parents, family income, access to land by family); and (iii) individual student-related variables (age, sex, personal interest in the subject, number of years living away from parents). These factors may be termed as student factors, family factors, school factors and peer factors (Crosnoe et al., 2004) but these factors may vary from person to person and place to place. Factors affecting student's performance can be investigated in terms of many variables of which some of them are parental involvement, homework and tutorial, class size, school facilities, teacher competency and principal's leadership. For instance, parents with higher income and education are more likely to have higher expectations for their children's educational attainment, have knowledge about their children's educational options and involve their children in intellectual activities (Cookson, 1994).

Factors affecting the academic performance of students at the secondary school are important issues for students. This study is also important because it examines the extent to which different types of factors at schools exert influence on the academic performance of

secondary school students. This paper may helpful for educational policy makers and administration to design and implement the policies to improve the students' performance. The main objective of this study is to find out the specific factors that affect the academic performance of students at secondary schools.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

To achieve the objectives of the study, the quantitative research approach was employed in this study. Quantitative research is a means for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables (Creswell, 2008). A descriptive method was used to gather the information on student's perceptions and experiences about different factors relating to academic performance of students in secondary schools. The major purpose of descriptive survey research design is a description of the state of affairs as it exists at present (Kothari, 2003). This survey allows collection of large amounts of data from the target population. The socio-economic status of the family, school related factors, teacher related factors, home related factors and student related factors affecting academic performance were the major theme of the questionnaire.

A total of eighty (80)secondary level students were selected on the basis of purposive sampling out of five community secondary schools in Tokha Municipality, Bagmati Province. A survey was conducted by using a questionnaire for information gathering about different factors relating to academic performance of students. Questionnaires are the most widely used instruments for collecting survey information and for providing structured, often numerical data, which are simple to tabulate, compare and analyze statistically (Cohen et al., 2007). The questionnaire prepared for students were administered in their regular class periods with the help of school teachers. The data obtained through questionnaires were edited, categorized tallied, and tabulated. The data were analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistics. Thus percentages mean types of statistical techniques were used to analyze the data secured through questionnaires. Percentage was used to explain the characteristics of the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

School Related Factors

School climate refers to the atmosphere created by staff and student behavior in the school. Positive school climate can yield positive educational outcomes for students and school staff. Conversely, a negative school climate can be a deterrent to effective instruction and student learning (Freiberg, 1998). Similarly Baughman

Table 1. School related factors affecting students' performance

Factors	Frequency	Percentage
School climate	59	73.75
Availability of teaching material	56	70.00
Method of lecture delivery	51	62.50
Overcrowded class rooms	47	58.75
Poor accommodation facilities	44	55.00
Poorly equipped libraries	40	50.00
Poor teacher/student relationship	37	46.25
Counseling and guidance	27	33.75
Interruption of electricity and water supply	15	18.75

(2000) found a strong correlation between school libraries and student performance. Lockheed and Verspoor (1991) report that the availability of textbooks and other instructional materials has a consistently positive effect on student performance in developing countries. McGuffey's (1982) study correlated student performance with better building quality, newer school buildings, better lighting, better thermal comfort and air quality, and more advanced laboratories and libraries. Table 1 above presents the frequency distribution of the school related factors considered by the respondents to affect their academic performance.

Majority of the respondents reported that school climate (73.75%), Availability of teaching material (70.00%), Method of lecture delivery (62.50%), Overcrowded class rooms (58.75%) were the factors that mostly affected their academic performance. Furthermore, the table shows that 55.00% of the respondents reported that the poor accommodation facilities and 50.00% of the respondent reported that poorly equipped libraries results affected their performance, while 46.25% of the respondents reported that poor teacher/student relationship also affected their academic performance. Results on the table also reveal that the rate of respondents' opinions on the other variables that affect their performance were low and below 40%, with the least (18.75%) being interruption of electricity and water supply. The institutional environment and facilities have significant impact on students' performance in secondary schools.

Teacher Related Factors

Teacher's educational level would seem to have a positive effect on student performance. Mbozi (2008) allude to teacher-pupil interaction as a factor that affects academic performance of learners. He found limited textbooks as a factor affecting the performance of the learners. The lack of teacher competence and not giving tests or examinations to the learners on a regular basis contributes to poor performance in academic work. Some schools performed poorly because of teacher related

factors such as, inadequate teacher preparation and teacher's lack of dedication to duty. Lack of motivation and professional commitment produce teacher's punctuality and unprofessional attitudes towards students which affect the performance of students. Musili (2015) observed that, when teachers are motivated, they are able to perform better, than when they are frustrated or ill motivated. If the teacher gives class exercises and does not mark them afterwards, then it will be very difficult for the teacher to know if the pupils have understood the lesson or not (Molokomphale and Mavis, 2014). Teacher preparation such as writing schemes, records of work and lesson-planning is a professional requirement for teachers in Zambia (Malambo, 2012). Table 2 below presents the frequency distribution of the teacher related factors considered by the respondents to affect their academic performance.

Majority of the respondents reported that teacher's motivation (86.25%), relation with their students, (76.25%), punctuality by teacher (72.50%), use of instructional materials (66.25%) were the factors that mostly affected their academic performance. Furthermore, the table shows that 52.50% of the respondents reported that the inadequate teacher preparedness and 45.00% of the respondent reported that non marking of student exercise affected their performance, while 36.25% of the respondents reported that teacher quality and commitment also affected their academic performance. Results on the table also reveal that the rate of respondents' opinions with the least (31.25%) being lack of qualified and experienced teachers. Teacher related factors have the major impact on teaching and learning process and students' performance.

Student Related Factors

Student related factors comprise a wide array of factors that determine the performance of students in learning. Motivation uplifts student's enthusiasm about the activities presented to them and attendance has a positive effect on students' academic performance.

Table 2. Teacher related factors affecting students' performance

Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Teachers motivation	69	86.25
Relation with their students	61	76.25
Punctuality by teachers	58	72.50
Use of instructional materials	53	66.25
Inadequate teacher preparedness	42	52.50
Non-marking of students exercises	36	45.00
Teachers quality and commitment to support students	29	36.25
Lack of qualified and experienced teachers	25	31.25

Table 3. Student related factors affecting students' performance

Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Students' self-motivation	68	85.00
Less amount of time invested on educational activities	65	81.25
Absence of regular school attendance	56	70.00
Relation with their teachers	52	65.00
Relation with other schoolmates	43	53.75
Lack of adequate effort	40	50.00
Lack of self confidence	35	43.75
Peer group influence	30	37.50
Inability to become well planned and organized	25	31.25

Academic performance of secondary school students was positively associated with their other classmates and teachers. Peer group influence also affect the academic performance of the students. Self-confidence is considered one of the most influential motivators which can affect performance when our efficacy expectation is strong and our abilities are clearly developed (Bandura, 1977). Students' adequate effort is strongly related to students' learning and academic performance. Table 3 above presents the frequency distribution of the student related factors considered by the respondents to affect their academic performance.

Majority of the respondents reported that students' self-motivation (85.00%), less amount of time invested on educational activities (81.25%), absence of regular school attendance (70.00%), and not positive relation with their teachers (65.00%) were the factors that mostly affected their academic performance. Furthermore, the table shows that 53.75% of the respondents reported that the not positive relation with other schoolmates and 50.00% of the respondent reported that lack of adequate effort results affected their performance, while 43.75% of the respondents reported that lack of self-confidence also affected their academic performance. Results on the table also reveal that the rate of respondents' opinions with the least (31.25%) being inability to become well planned and organized. Student related factors have the major impact on teaching and learning process and their performance.

Parent Related Factors

Parents provide school supplies, supervision of activities, and home environments that are learner friendly (Bauch, 1994; Epstein, 1995). Successful parent involvement can be defined as the active, ongoing participation of a parent or primary caregiver in the education of his or her child. The most basic involvement of parents in their child's schooling is provision of basic needs. Parental education and family socio-economic status have positive correlations with the students' quality of achievement (Jeynes, 2002). Parents can also participate in school management committee, parent-teacher organizations and other committee involved in decision making for their school. Factors such as income, parent's education and occupation, regularity of teachers, interest created by the teachers in the subject and interest of the students in the co-curricular activities were found to play a major role in determining academic performance of students (Daniyal et al., 2011). Table 4 below presents the frequency distribution of the parent related factors considered by the respondents to affect their academic performance.

Majority of the respondents reported that socio-economic status of parents (82.50%), parents academic background (81.25%), parental occupation level (75.00%), and parents attitude towards academic performance (62.50%) were the factors that mostly affected their academic performance. Furthermore, the table shows that 52.50% of the respondents reported that poor parent-child interaction results affected their performance while 38.75% of the respondents reported

Table 4. Parent related factors affecting students' performance

Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Parents socio-economic status	66	82.50
Parents academic background	65	81.25
Parental occupation level	60	75.00
Attitude towards academic performance	50	62.50
Poor parental-child interaction	42	52.50
Home environment	31	38.75
Family size	28	35.00

that home environment also affected their academic performance. Results on the table also reveal that the rate of respondents' opinions with the least (35.00%) being family size. Parents are the major component of teaching and learning process and students' performance. These prominent factors are socio economic status, academic background and occupation level of parents.

CONCLUSIONS

Research was conducted on community secondary schools in Tokha Municipality, Bagmati Province. There are a number of factors inside and outside the school which influence the quality of academic performance of student's school level. This study focused on some of the school, teacher, student and parent related factors that influence the student's performances. It has been found that the factors that affect students' academic performance was a multidimensional issues. Based on findings, school climate, availability of teaching materials, methods of delivery were the major school related factors that affect students' academic performance. Teacher related factors which mostly affect academic performance of student were teacher's motivation, relation with their students, punctuality by teachers, use of instructional materials, inadequate teacher preparedness, non-marking of student's exercises. Student related major factors are student's self-motivation, less amount of time invested on educational activities, absence of regular school attendance, relation with teachers, relation with other schoolmates, lack of adequate effort etc. socio economic status, parents academic background, parental occupation level, attitude towards academic performance, poor parental child interaction were the parent related factors that affect students' academic performance. The policy makers, school authority, teachers and parents must aware to improve the students' academic performance at secondary schools. To reduce negative factors that affect students' academic performance in secondary schools, the concerned peoples and institutions have to work seriously. Further policy setting and revising of current educational policy is required to improve the academic performance of the students.

Secondary school authority should adopt motivational programs that will increase students' academic performance.

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